

SURFACE FUNCTIONALIZED CNTS GRAFTED SHORT CARBON FIBERS IN CFRP COMPOSITES AS INTERLEAVING TOUGHENER AND DAMAGE SENSOR

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ABSTRACT

Surface functionalized carbon nanotubes (CNT) were in-situ deposited and grafted onto non-woven short carbon fiber (SCF) tissue by a simple ethanol flame synthesis method and the resulted CNT-SCFs were used as interleaving materials for toughening carbon fabric/epoxy composites. When these hierarchical carbon structures were used as interleaves in carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) composites, significant improvement (125%) in mode I interlaminar fracture energy of CFRP laminates was achieved with an areal density of 1.0 mg/cm² CNT-SCFs when compared to the control laminates. Results indicated a positive synergistic toughening effect. Moreover, the crack damage sensing capacity of the toughened CFRP composites with a simple electrical response method was investigated theoretically based on a parallel resistance model and demonstrated by the experiments, where the electrical resistance change increased almost monotonously with crack increment and fits well with the calculations. Useful guideline for high crack sensing design of the laminate composite and electrical measurement were resulted.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) composites have been widely used in various structure engineering fields, e.g., aircrafts, automobiles, etc., owing to their excellent specific mechanical properties. However, their poor delamination resistance has seriously limited many practical applications. Many techniques have been developed to improve the fracture toughness of these CFRPs, including Z-pinning, interleaving and stitching at failure-prone regions of composites structures [1]. Various conductive carbon fillers (such as carbon black, short carbon fibres (SCFs), CNTs and CNFs) were investigated as functional reinforcements in the polymer composites.

The development of hierarchical multi-scale reinforcement for CFRP composites by in situ growing CNTs onto the fabric surface has been demonstrated as an efficient method to improve functional properties of the composites, including their mechanical properties [2]. CNTs used in the carbon fabrics can be fabricated prior to or in situ grown. After the CNTs are grafted onto the CFs, the interfacial property of the final composite depends on both CNT/matrix interface and the anchorage of CNTs-CF. In CFRPs composites, the dominant failure mechanism could be mainly controlled by the grafting force of CNTs onto CFs in some cases [3].

Carbon fiber is a multifunctional reinforcement for CFRPs due to its lightweight, good chemical and thermal stability, high electrical and thermal conductivities, and superior mechanical properties. Its high thermal stability makes it suitable to be the fiber substrate for in situ growth of CNTs. Therefore, hierarchical carbon-based reinforcement can be achieved by in situ growing CNTs onto CFs and this is found to be an efficient way to improving the interfacial properties [4]. The advantages of this technique over those dispersing the preformed CNTs into CFRPs are better distribution, higher density, and even control of orientation in the composites. Among various in-situ CNT growth methods, chemical vapor deposition (CVD) is the most utilized for growing CNTs onto CFs [5]. Compared to CVD methods, the flame growth of CNTs onto CFs is developed very recently, and the strong adhesion of in situ flame synthesized CNTs onto CF has been proven [6].

Following our previous work on toughening CFRPs by SCF interleaves or by in situ flame grown CNTs onto carbon fabrics, we will report here our recent results on CFRP laminates interleaved with a hierarchical structure based on SCFs grafted with the surface functionalized CNTs to increase their delamination toughness. The CNTs were directly deposited and grafted onto SCFs by the flame synthesis method developed recently in our Lab. Then, they were used as interleaving materials in the laminates. Moreover, the in-situ health monitoring and damage detection of engineering structures are important and highly desirable in the real applications. Incorporation of the hierarchical CNT-SCF reinforcements in epoxy resin rich regions within the interlayer is expected to provide an in-situ damage sensing capability of these interleaved CFRP laminates. This particular aspect will also be presented.

2. EXPERIMENTAL WORK

2.1 Raw materials

Materials used in this study included plain woven carbon fabrics (Inter-Turbine Advanced logistics Pty Ltd, Australia) for the CFRPs laminates composites and SCFs preparation, the epoxy resin system made of Araldite-F (diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A, DGEBA) and piperidine (Sigma-Aldrich), and surfactant (hydroxypropylmethylcellulose, Sigma-Aldrich).

2.2 CNT-SCF fabrication

The woven carbon fabrics were manually chopped into carbon fiber bundles with around 1cm in length. The aqueous dispersion containing chopped carbon fiber, and surfactant was stirred and cutting further by the blades for about 30min to obtain the uniform dispersion of chopped short carbon fibers (SCFs) in the solution. After filtration of the dispersion and rinsed with distilled water to remove the residual surfactant, a non-woven SCF (NWSCF) tissue was obtained. The tissue was infiltrated with NiCl_2 solution before being inserted into the ethanol flame for deposition of the functionalized CNTs. The growth of CNTs was completed within 3mins.

2.3 CFRP laminate fabrication

A calculated amount of SCFs or CNT-SCFs was dispersed in acetone assisted by ultrasonic irradiation. Then, epoxy resin was added into the solution followed by magnetic stirring for 0.5 h to achieve better dispersion. After removing the acetone in a vacuum oven, the curing agent was added. The resin and curing agent were mixed in weight ratio of 100:5. The CFRP laminates were fabricated with plain woven carbon fabrics and epoxy resin by hand lay-up as reported in [7]. Finally, the samples for tests were cut by a diamond saw.

2.4 Characterization

All the mechanical properties tests were performed on an Instron 5567 machine. Mode I interlaminar fracture energy, G_{IC} , were measured following ASTM D5528-01. The propagation interlaminar fracture energy ($G_{IC,Pro}$) was the average G_{IC} value when the crack growth was increased in the plateau region of the R-curve. At least three samples were tested for each material system. As depicted elsewhere[8], for the in-situ damage/crack increment sensing tests, 2 thin conductive wires were positioned along the width of the end-faces of the double-cantilever-beams with conductive silver paste to improve the electrical contact. The two electrodes were connected to a CHI electrochemical workstation for real time measurements. A constant potential was applied and the instantaneous current was recorded continuously as the crack propagated. Optical microscopy (OM)

was performed on an Olympus DM. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images were conducted on a JEOL 2200FS (200 kV).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 The in situ growth of CNTs onto NWSCF-tissue

Fig. 1 (a) The morphology of carbon fabric before; (b) non-woven SCF tissue.

As shown in Figure 1a, the carbon fibers in the original plain woven carbon fabrics are in a form of continuous bundles which are interweaving across each other, and the fabric surface is clean and tidy. In contrast, it can be seen that the NWSCF tissue displayed much rougher surface and SCFs are randomly distributed in the tissue and formed a non-woven network (Fig. 1b). Such a structure benefits the infiltration of catalyst precursor solution and the following in-situ growth of CNTs on more fiber surface. Moreover, it is easy for the resulted CNT-SCFs in the tissue to be re-dispersed in resins.

Fig.2 CNTs growth on a SCF

Different from most CVD process, where the metal catalyst particles were usually prepared prior to the deposition of CNTs, the nickel catalyst used here are formed in situ from a very cheap precursor NiCl_2 . [4,6] The catalysts are in a form of Ni@C core-shell structure, and CNTs grow from them on the surface of SCFs, as shown in the Fig. 2. The CNTs growth can be completed within 3mins. The CNTs have a diameter of ~ 20 nm. The thermal stability of the bare CFs in the flame and the reducing atmosphere in the flame protects the SCFs and the resulted CNTs from combustion. This means that our flame growth method is much simpler and faster than most CVD processes.

Because of the low temperature, one-step procedure, short time and reducing atmosphere in the flame growth process, there was no evident decrease of the tensile strength [4]. Moreover, both the electrical conductivity and interfacial shear strength of CFs were improved significantly after the CNTs were growth for only 3 minutes. Electron microscopy studies revealed that both tip and root growth mechanisms were involved during the flame-induced synthesis [4].

Some oxygen-containing functional groups on CNTs can be formed by the flame synthesis method [4]. Their existence is believed to be a distinct advantage of flame synthesized CNTs over conventional CNTs by CVD, as they can readily establish hydrogen bonding with epoxy. Thus, the affinity of CNT-SCF to epoxy is effectively increased.

3.2. Fracture toughness results

The influences of SCF or CNT-SCF interleaves on mode I interlaminar fracture initiation G_{IC} of CFRP laminates were studied, and some results were published elsewhere just recently [7]. Fig.3a displayed the typical R-curve of the CFRPs samples, and $G_{IC, Pro}$ propagation values were calculated and used as an indicator to evaluate the toughening effects by the interleaves. These propagation fracture toughness energies are given in Fig 3b, which showed that, $G_{IC, Pro}$ is significantly increased by the interleaves. Compared to the control sample, the increases in fracture energy is 73% by 1.0 mg/cm² SCF interleaves. Further increases of 125% are achieved by 1.0 mg/cm² CNT-SCF interleaves. The slight decrease in $G_{IC, Pro}$ with interleaves of higher areal density can be attributed to the imperfect diffusion of epoxy resin into the high areal density SCF or CNT-SCF interleaves.

Fig.3. (a) typical R-curve of CFRPs samples; (b) $G_{IC,Pro}$ of CFRP laminates [7]

In comparison with our previous work [2], where the same flame synthesis method was adopted to graft CNTs onto the carbon fabrics, the present measured ΔG_{IC} of 0.65 kJ/m² of the laminates interleaved with 1.0 mg/cm² CNT-SCF is much higher, and the value is also larger than that ΔG_{IC} of 0.38 kJ/m² due to the 1.0 mg/cm² SCF interleaves. These suggests a positive synergistic toughening effect by the hierarchical nano-sized CNTs grafted on micro-sized SCFs, and could be caused by the grafted CNTs improving the interfacial bonding between SCFs and matrix and simultaneously enhancing the toughness contributions due to CNT bridging and pullout, as shown in Fig.4.

Fig. 4 Schematic diagram of CNT-SCF fiber bridging

3.3 In-situ damage crack sensing

Fig. 5 (a) In-situ damage sensing result of CNT-SCF interleaved laminates, (b) normalized crack growth as a function of normalized electrical resistance change

Different from those damage detecting of FRPs based on the electrical response along the fiber longitudinal direction under tensile or flexure loading, our in-situ crack propagation capability of the CFRPs are demonstrated by detecting crack growth during DCB tests. The proposed sensing method is based on the through-thickness resistance change of the failure-prone region between the carbon fabrics in the laminate [8]. The electrical sensing signal changed with the cracking load and corresponding crack increment, which could be used to detect crack growth in the composites.

As shown in Fig. 5a, a series of stick-slips in applied load with increasing displacement are observed during DCB testing, corresponding to the events of crack growth and arrest. With each crack increment, the through-thickness electrical resistance increases step by step, indicating the reliability of the in situ sensing technique with electrical resistance measurements.

For real applications of damage detection, the damage sensitivity interpreted by the response of the electrical signal (resistance R or current I) with crack increment (Δa) is more desirable. As shown in Fig. 5b, the experiment on interleaved CFRP samples indicates that the normalized resistance change ($\Delta R/R_0$) increases monotonously with normalized crack growth $\Delta a/c$, demonstrating the capability of continuous in-situ monitoring of crack increment by the electrical resistance method.

Fig.6 Schematic showing the change in electrical current with crack increment

To understand the crack sensing of our method, we build a simple model, where we assume that the whole through-thickness resistance of the failure prone interlayer between the middle two plies of carbon fabrics in CFRPs (R_t) is made of lots of parallel resistance (R_u) along the interlayer between the fabrics in CFRP, as shown in Fig.6. As the structure of CFRP is uniform and all the parallel resistance could be the same and distributed uniformly. Then, the relationship between the electrical response and crack increment is calculated according to Ohm' s law:

$$R = R_x + R_t \quad (1)$$

where R is total circuit resistance, which comprise of two parts, i.e. R_t and R_x . R_x is the resistance owing to other parts in the circuit which include the resistance of carbon fibers along the longitudinal direction, the interface resistance between the metal wire electrodes and carbon fibers in the silver paste, and inner resistance commonly present with the two-probe method. To simply the calculation, we also assume $R_x = nR_{t0}$. The measured resistance R_0 with no crack growth is given by:

$$R_0 = R_x + R_{t0} = (n + 1)R_{t0} \quad (2)$$

$$R_{t0} = R_u/m \quad (3)$$

With the crack growth of Δa , y resistance units were broken, therefore,

$$\Delta a = cy/m \quad (4)$$

And the resistance will be:

$$R = R_x + R_t = R_x + [mR_{t0}/(m-y)] \quad (5)$$

where m is the number of the whole resistance units without crack, y the number of the broken resistance after the crack increment of Δa , R_u the resistance of each unit, Δa is crack increment and c is the length from the pre-crack tip to the end of the sample, as indicated in Figure 6. The normalized resistance change with normalized crack increment becomes:

$$(R-R_0)/R_0 = \{y/(m-y)\}/(n+1) = \{(\Delta a/c)/(1-\Delta a/c)\}/(n+1) \quad (6)$$

The equation is just the same as that we calculated based on another model[8]. According to equation (6), depending on the ratio n between R_x and R_{t0} , the normalized resistance change $(R-R_0)/R_0$ with normalized crack increment $\Delta a/c$ is very different. In the ideal case of $R_x = 0$, the highest sensitivity to crack increment can be achieved. With increasing value of R_x , the sensitivity decreases correspondingly. Based on our experiment results, we found that when $n=4.5$, the experimental data give good fit to the theoretical values (Fig.5b), indicating the presence of non-negligible resistance of R_x in the electrical measurements. Thus, a useful guideline for high damage sensitive design of the laminate composite and the electrical measurement is to maximize R_{t0} and minimize R_x , although it is difficult to remove R_x completely in real circumstances.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Short carbon fibers (SCFs) grafted with carbon nanotubes (CNTs) were used as CNT-SCF interleaves to increase the mode I delamination fracture energy G_{IC} of CFRP composite laminates. Even at a relatively low CNT-SCF areal density, 1.0 mg/cm^2 , G_{IC} was increased by 125%, indicating a highly improved performance compared to those results obtained by other interleaving methods. Results also revealed synergistic toughening mechanisms in these CNT-SCF interleaved CFRP laminates. The damage sensing capability of the CNT-SCFs interleaved CFRP composites were proven. The electrical sensing signal changed with the cracking load and corresponding crack propagation, which could be used to detect damage in CFRP composites. A simple parallel resistance model for the crack sensing experiments was developed and the calculation results show that the damage sensitivity depends on the ratio between the interlayer resistance and the sum of resistances caused by carbon fabrics in the DCB laminates, wiring, contacts and the measurement devices. The higher the ratio, the larger the crack sensing sensitivity of the interleaves. It is believed that the CNT-SCF hierarchical structural interleaves endow the multi-functionality of the CFRP composites.

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